

SEE and beam characterization with high-energy heavy ions at HIMAC

Matteo Cecchetto, Kacper Bilko, Natalia Emriskova, Rubén García Alía, *Member IEEE*, Satoshi Kodaira, Jean-Luc Aufran

Abstract—Single event effect cross sections and energy deposition events in silicon diodes were measured with high-energy heavy ions at HIMAC, in Japan, by varying LETs through PMMA degraders. Primary beam energies of 178 MeV/n ^{132}Xe and 320 MeV/n ^{84}Kr , measured at the device under test position, were employed. Results were compared to those from other heavy ion facilities, highlighting the importance of facility inter-comparisons. Considerations about single event upset cross sections, measured with and without the package and with fully fragmented beams, are outlined.

Index Terms—HIMAC, high-energy, heavy ions, SRAMs, diode, COTS

I. INTRODUCTION

HIGH-energy heavy ion beams (hundreds of MeV/n) have several advantages with respect to using standard energies (tens of MeV/n) when measuring single event effect (SEE) cross sections, linked to the high penetration properties of the beam in materials, as well as to their closer resemblance to the space radiation environment. For instance, typical heavy ion irradiations are performed in vacuum and by removing the package of electronic chips to allow the beam to reach the sensitive volume with a defined linear energy transfer (LET), a preparation process which is not needed with high energy beams. However, facilities offering such beams are very limited in number and availability worldwide. In the framework of developing the capability to provide high energy heavy ion beams for electronics testing at CERN (e.g., for space applications) [1], tests with 178 MeV/n ^{132}Xe and 320 MeV/n ^{84}Kr ions at the Heavy Ion Medical Accelerator in Chiba (HIMAC) facility in Japan were performed and are presented in this work. The tests were carried out during two test campaigns with four hours of Xe ions in 2024 and six hours of Kr ions in 2025, with beamtime granted through scientific proposal. Single event upsets (SEUs) and single event latch-up (SEUs) were measured in static random access memories (SRAMs), and the energy deposition events induced by the beam were recorded in silicon diodes. These devices are used as a means of comparison and calibration between facilities, and the purpose of this work is to assess

the compatibility of results between HIMAC and other heavy ion facilities, in particular HEARTS at CERN [1]. This study also aims to highlight possible differences when testing the memories with and without the package using high-energy heavy ion beams. SEE cross sections are measured at several LETs obtained by degrading the primary ion beam through polymethyl-methacrylate (PMMA) slabs, including tests with fully fragmented beams. Silicon diodes were used to measure the ion flux for monitoring purposes and to study the beam composition (due to e.g. fragmentation).

II. HIMAC HIGH ENERGY HEAVY ION FACILITY

The HIMAC facility [2], [3], primarily dedicated to heavy ion radiotherapy, is located at the National Institute for Quantum and Radiological Science and Technology (QST), in Chiba, Japan. Irradiations for these studies were performed in the HIMAC BIO room, which is dedicated to biology and physics experiments. Several ions are available, ranging from 100 to 800 MeV/n. The tests presented in this work were performed using an energy of 178 MeV/n (^{132}Xe ions) and 320 MeV/n (^{84}Kr ions), measured at the device under test (DUT) position.

Ions are accelerated in the main synchrotron and extracted with a primary energy of 290 MeV/n (Xe) and 400 MeV/n (Kr). As the beam travels in air and through monitoring instrumentation, the beam energy at the DUT position was measured by the facility to be 178 MeV/n (Xe) and 320 MeV/n (Kr) from a Bragg's curve dose calibration using a Markus ionisation chamber [4]. The ion beam is delivered in pulses every 3.3 s, with a width of roughly 1 s. The beam size of 6 cm and 10 cm in diameter for the Xe and Kr beams, respectively, with a homogeneity of $\pm 5\%$, allowed for testing several devices at the same time. The flux can span from roughly 10 up to 10^5 ions/cm²/s, and the total fluence was monitored online by means of a plastic scintillator close to the DUT and an ionisation chamber (IC) positioned upstream the setup and the degraders. During the 2024 test campaign with Xe ions, a plastic scintillator with an area of 1 cm² was located next to the DUT, while in 2025 with Kr ions, a different plastic scintillator with an area of 20x20 cm² was installed between the DUTs and the PMMAs. The primary beam energy was degraded through PMMA slabs with a density of 1.19 g/cm³, in order to increase the LET of the beam. Several PMMA degraders (binary filters) are available at the facility, and different thicknesses can be obtained by combining them. Table I reports the PMMA thicknesses used in this work for both Xe and Kr ions. The thicknesses of the degraders to be used were chosen to have a range of LETs suitable for

M. Cecchetto is with CERN, CH-1211 Geneva, Switzerland and IM2NP, Aix-Marseille University, CNRS, F-13397 Marseille, France.

K. Bilko and R. García Alía are with CERN, CH-1211 Genève, Switzerland. N. Emriskova is with CERN, CH-1211 Geneva, Switzerland and IES, Montpellier University, F-34090 Montpellier, France.

Satoshi Kodaira is with National Institutes for Quantum Science and Technology (QST), Chiba, Japan.

J. L. Aufran is with IPR, Rennes University, CNRS, F-35042 Rennes, France.

E-mail: matteo.cecchetto@cern.ch

TABLE I

PMMA THICKNESSES USED DURING THE TESTS WITH THE CORRESPONDING EXIT BEAM ENERGY AND LETS IN Si CALCULATED THROUGH SRIM AND FLUKA. PRIMARY ENERGY OF 178 AND 320 MEV/N FOR ^{132}Xe AND ^{84}Kr , RESPECTIVELY. ‘FRAG’ DENOTES FULL BEAM FRAGMENTATION, BASED ON SRIM PREDICTIONS (BLUE, ITALIC) AND ON MEASUREMENTS FROM THIS WORK (BOLD)

Ion	PMMA [mm]	Exit Energy [MeV/n]	LET SRIM [MeVcm ² /mg]	LET FLUKA [MeVcm ² /mg]
^{132}Xe	0	178	11.9	11.2
	3.5	131	14	13.4
	4	122	14.6	14.2
	5	106	16.2	15.3
	5.5	98	17.2	
	6.5	78	20.2	
	7	67	22.7	20.6
	7.5	54	25.4	23.3
	8	39	31.5	28.0
	8.5	19	47.4	
	9	-	<i>frag₁</i>	
9.5	-	<i>frag₂</i>		
10.5	-	<i>frag₃</i>		
^{84}Kr	10	320	3.6	3.55
	20	179	5.0	5.25
	25	131	6.1	6.55
	28	95	7.7	8.65
	30	65	9.9	12.95
	30.5	57	11.0	16.15
	31	46	<i>frag₄</i> (12.62)	
	31.5	34	<i>frag₅</i> (15.44)	
	32	18	<i>frag₆</i> (23.17)	

the devices to be tested, including a full fragmentation of the beam. The energy of the residual beam after passing through the PMMA (exit energy) and corresponding LET in silicon are calculated via the stopping and range of ions in matter (SRIM) 2013 tool [5]. LETs were also calculated using FLUKA Monte Carlo simulations, as reported in Table I. For the Xe beam, the simulations yielded slightly lower values than those obtained with SRIM. Differently, the LETs for Kr simulated in [6] were found to be larger for thicker PMMAs compared to those obtained with SRIM.

Moreover, according to SRIM, the range of the 178 MeV/n Xe beam on PMMA is 8.78 mm, hence, the beam is expected to be fully fragmented for PMMA thicknesses greater than or equal to 9 mm. However, as it will be shown, the measurements performed in this work suggest that the range was roughly 0.7 mm longer, and a high LET beam was still present with PMMAs of 9 and 9.5 mm. Instead, the range of the 320 MeV/n Kr beam on PMMA is 32.5 mm according to SRIM, while measurements indicated that the beam was fully fragmented already at 31.5 mm, hence, the range was 1 cm shorter. The LET values in parentheses for the Kr beams in Table I are extracted from SRIM, although the measurements in this work indicated that these beams were already fragmented.

III. DIODE FLUENCE CROSS-CALIBRATION AND FRAGMENTATION ASSESSMENT

Silicon diode detectors were employed to provide a fluence measurement independent of the facility scintillator and to obtain energy deposition spectra for studying beam fragmentation [7]. Such detectors are crucial for the HEARTS project

Fig. 1. Diode energy deposition induced by the 178 MeV/n Xe ion beam for various PMMA thicknesses. Full beam fragmentation occurred with 10.5 mm.

and related activities at CERN, as it is the primary beam instrumentation used for intensity calibration [8].

A. Xe beam diode measurement

A fully depleted silicon diode with a thickness of 300 μm , model Canberra FD50-14-300RM, was employed during the Xe runs to provide an additional fluence measurement. The diode has an exposed active surface of 0.5 cm^2 and was biased at 60 V. The fluence provided by the diode (for non-fragmented beams), calculated as the ratio between energy deposition events induced by the beam and its active area, generally overestimated the scintillator fluence by an average of 30%, with a maximum deviation of up to 47%.

The energy deposition spectra of the Xe beam measured by the diode, by varying the PMMA degrader thickness, are presented in Fig. 1. For thicknesses below 6 mm, the spectra feature two direct-ionisation peaks. The more prominent peak is induced by ions hitting the silicon directly, as part of the diode active area is exposed, while the rest is covered by its metal housing. The second peak, at higher deposited energy, is induced by ions that were degraded in the detector's case, leading to an increase in their LET. The degrader of 6 mm together with the detector housing form a configuration where the stopping power is closer to the Bragg peak, leading to the high energy tail, which starts to vanish due to its full stopping with thicker PMMAs (e.g. with 7.5 mm). The energy deposition peak due to ions directly hitting silicon can be clearly identified until a PMMA thickness of 8 mm. Due to energy loss, increasing the PMMA thickness brings the spectrum closer to the Bragg peak region, where the spread in energy deposition becomes larger. In the 9.0 mm case, the measured deposited energy is the highest, due to the combination of prior degradation (boosting the LET but reducing the energy) and remaining ions' kinetic energy. In the 9.5 mm case, the silicon detector still measured some high-energy deposition events likely due to the presence of a heavily degraded beam, with remaining range in silicon below the

Fig. 2. Diode energy deposition induced by the 320 MeV/n Ke ion beam for various PMMA thicknesses. Full beam fragmentation occurred with 31.5 mm and was nearly reached with 31 mm.

detector's thickness. Finally, the beam was fully fragmented with 10.5 mm PMMA thickness, with no remaining Xe ions and consisting of secondary particles with lower LET. Hence, contrary to SRIM simulations, the beam was not fully fragmented with 9 and 9.5 mm PMMAs.

B. Kr beam diode measurement

A silicon diode from Micron Semiconductor Ltd., model MSX002 (SS) 300 2M/2M, was used to measure the Kr beam. The active surface of the diode is $2 \times 2 \text{ mm}^2$, with a thickness of $300 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$ and was biased at 80 V . The fluence provided by the diode (for non-fragmented beams) underestimated the scintillator fluence by an average of 30%, with a maximum underestimation of up to 60%. The energy deposition spectra measured by the diode with Kr ions are presented in Fig. 2, and their shape allows similar considerations as for the Xe beam. According to the diode measurements, the primary Kr beam was present up to a PMMA thickness of 30.5 mm and was fully fragmented at 31.5 mm. The spectrum with 31 mm of PMMA shows a boundary: the peak is very broad, with a lower maximum energy than that obtained with the 30.5 mm degrader, indicating that the Bragg peak was likely surpassed and the beam populated by many fragments. The range of the 320 MeV/n Kr beam on PMMA provided by SRIM is 32.5 mm, therefore, at least 1 cm longer with respect to the diode measurements.

IV. DEVICES UNDER TEST

The DUTs are commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) SRAMs tested against SEU and SEL, which are listed in Table II. The date codes 1713 and 1919 of the Cypress memory identify the delidded and packaged versions, respectively, while the other memories had a single date code. All devices were powered at 3.3 V and tested in air, at room temperature. SEU-sensitive memories were tested both with the package and without it (delidded, exposing the sensitive area of the chip) to assess the penetration properties of the high energy ion

Fig. 3. SEU-sensitive SRAMs (on the left) and diode setup (in the center) irradiated at HIMAC with Xe ions. The scintillator was installed next to the diode on its right during the Xe test campaign in 2024.

TABLE II
SEE TESTED COTS SRAMs. CYPRESS MEMORY WITH DATE CODES 1713 AND 1919 ARE DELIDDED AND PACKAGED, RESPECTIVELY

DUT	SEE	Size Mbit	Reference	Date code	Tech. nm
ISSI	SEU	32	IS61WV204816BLL-10TLI	1650	40
Cypress	SEU	16	CY62167GE30-45ZXI	1713-1919	65
Renesas	SEU	8	RMLV0816BGSA-4S2	9062	110
Samsung	SEL	4	K6R4016V1D-TC10	1650	180

beam. The SEU-tested memories were initially written with a checkerboard pattern (01) and read/rewritten every 5 s through a motherboard controlled via a laptop. A photograph of the setup is shown in Fig. 3, where two SRAMs and the diode were irradiated simultaneously. The SEL setup consisted of a single memory (with package) in standby mode, whose current was monitored via software to detect SELs. For the Samsung memory, the current threshold was set to 10 mA , hold time to 0.6 s and reset time to 1 s .

V. SEE CROSS SECTIONS RESULTS AND COMPARISON

The HIMAC SEE cross sections are presented and compared with results from other heavy ion facilities. These facilities include RADEF (Jyvaskyla, Finland), KVI (Groningen, The Netherlands), GANIL (Caen, France), and HEARTS at CERN (Geneva, Switzerland). The uncertainty associated with the HIMAC SEE cross sections is calculated with 95% confidence level, considering both event statistics and fluence ($\pm 10\%$) uncertainties. The former uncertainty is modelled as a Poisson distribution when more than 50 events (N_{SEE}) are recorded with standard deviation $\sigma_{\text{stat}} = \pm\sqrt{N_{\text{SEE}}}$. As SEU events were generally larger than 1000, the associated statistical uncertainty is lower than 3%, hence, the final uncertainty is dominated by fluence uncertainty. When the events were fewer than 50, instead, the statistical uncertainty was calculated considering lower and upper limits from [9], which extend a Poisson distribution.

Fig. 4. ISSI SRAM SEU cross sections comparison, shown for delidded and packaged (lid) memories. The Weibull functions are shown considering data measurements from different heavy ion facilities (RADEF, KVI, GANIL, HEARTS). HIMAC Weibull parameters: $\sigma_{\text{sat}} = 1 \cdot 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^2/\text{bit}$, $\text{LET}_{\text{th}}=0.2 \text{ MeV} \cdot \text{cm}^2/\text{mg}$, $W=23.32$, $s=1.12$.

A. SEU cross sections

The HIMAC SEU cross sections of the ISSI, Cypress and Renesas memories are shown in Figs. 4, 5 and 6, respectively, for both packaged and delidded tests. SEU cross sections are calculated considering all bit flips that occurred in the memory, and numerical values are reported in Tables IV, V and VI. The tables report the number of SEU, single bit upsets (SBU) and multiple bit upsets (MBU). SEU denotes the total number of bit flips, given by the sum of SBU and MBU, with the latter referring to the total number of flipped bits from multiple events (events times their multiplicity) The fluence used for the SEE cross section calculations is that provided by the scintillator of the facility. The comparison of the ISSI cross sections is performed considering a Weibull function from data measured at RADEF, KVI and GANIL from [10] and that obtained including HEARTS data from [11]. The Cypress cross sections are compared with two Weibull fits, obtained from measurements at KVI and GANIL [10], and at RADEF, respectively. The Renesas Weibull is that calculated from measurements at GSI and HEARTS from [11].

The SEU cross sections of the ISSI memory measured with both Xe and Kr ions at HIMAC are in good agreement with the Weibull fits measured in other facilities (Fig. 4). The Cypress cross sections measured at HIMAC are significantly lower with respect to the expected Weibull function, with differences of up to one order of magnitude (Fig. 5). The discrepancy is likely related to the prevalence of MBUs, given that at HIMAC most bit flips were due to MBUs rather than SBUs, with a ratio of 1.55:1, whereas in other facilities MBUs were negligible. All Cypress measurements at HIMAC, during both test campaigns (Xe and Kr ions), with both delidded and packaged memories, showed the same high number of MBUs with respect to SBUs. The distribution of events in time and across the logical map of the Cypress memory was confirmed to be nominal. Significant discrepancies with respect to the expected Weibull fit were

Fig. 5. Cypress SRAM SEU cross sections comparison, shown for delidded and packaged (lid) memories. The Weibull function is that from data measurements at KVI and GANIL, and RADEF.

Fig. 6. Renesas SRAM SEU cross sections comparison, shown for delidded and packaged (lid) memories. The Weibull function is that from data measurements at GSI and HEARTS.

also found in the Renesas memory (Fig. 6). While the Xe SEU cross sections agree with the Weibull fit (from HEARTS and GSI), the Kr measurements indicate high sensitivity below the expected LET threshold, for both packaged samples (see Fig. 6). The average fraction of bit flips due to MBUs in the Renesas memory was 11% at HIMAC compared to 29% at HEARTS.

The ISSI SEU cross sections measured with the package were in general higher than those with the delidded chip by up to 70%, which is expected, as the beam will lose some energy inside the package, resulting in a higher LET when reaching the sensitive volume of the memory. However, in the Renesas memory, the SEU cross sections with the package were always lower by up to one order of magnitude, which could also be related to part-to-part variability. Differences of up to a factor of three were observed in the Cypress memory.

Fig. 7. Renesas SEU cross sections comparison calculated using LETs simulated through FLUKA and the fluence from the diode measurements.

B. SEU cross section with LET from simulations

As previously seen, especially for the Renesas memory measured with Kr ions, the SEU cross sections resulted shifted to lower LETs with respect to the cross sections measured in other facilities. To cross-check the LET extracted via SRIM, FLUKA Monte Carlo simulations were performed in [6], and the simulated LETs are reported in Table I. Fig. 7 shows the Renesas cross sections calculated using the fluence from the diode and the LET simulated through FLUKA, in comparison to those from Fig. 6, calculated using the fluence of the scintillator of the facility and LET from SRIM. Although the simulated LETs are higher than those obtained from SRIM, they are still below the LET threshold expected from HEARTS and GSI.

C. SEU cross sections with fully fragmented beam

A noteworthy comparison concerns the SEU cross sections obtained with a fully fragmented beam, i.e., when the beam was completely stopped in the PMMA and only secondary particles reached the device. To notice that these cross sections were calculated using the scintillator fluence, which acts as a counter for all particles above a threshold. However, the SEU cross sections do not have the canonical meaning, and a more detailed analysis regarding fragmented runs will be presented in [12].

For both the ISSI and Renesas memories (Tables IV and VI, respectively), the SEU cross sections obtained with the fully fragmented Xe beam (frag₃, 10.5 mm PMMA) were essentially the same as those measured at one of the highest LET values of 31.5 MeV·cm²/mg. As previously seen, the diode measurements confirmed that the beam was fully fragmented. If the fluence upstream of the degraders (from the IC) were used, both SEU cross sections would be lower by a factor of 62, since the IC fluence was larger than that measured by the scintillator at the DUT position. A similar behavior, though less pronounced, was observed for the Renesas memory with Kr ions, where the SEU cross sections with fragmented beams

Fig. 8. Samsung SRAM SEL cross sections comparison. Memories tested with the package.

TABLE III
SAMSUNG 180 NM MEMORY - SEL CROSS SECTIONS MEASURED AT HIMAC WITH 178 MEV/N XE AND 320 MEV/N KR ION BEAMS, FOR PACKAGED MEMORIES

Ion	PMMA [mm]	LET SRIM [MeVcm ² /mg]	Packaged SEL	$\sigma_{\text{deljddd}}^{\text{SEL}}$ [cm ² /bit]	$\pm 2\sigma$ %
Xe	5	16.2	53	$9.44 \cdot 10^{-4}$	29
	25	6.1	1	$5.21 \cdot 10^{-7}$	-90 +460
Kr	28	7.7	17	$3.66 \cdot 10^{-5}$	+60
	30	9.9	5	$5.62 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-68 +134

(frag_{4,5,6}) and defined based on the scintillator fluence were comparable to that preceding the maximum value. In addition, for the Renesas and Cypress memories, which were measured using a broader range of LETs and fragmented Xe beams, the frag₂ SEU cross sections increased of several factors compared to those measured with the highest LET of 47.4 MeVcm²/mg. These results are coherent with the diode spectra in Fig. 1, suggesting that the beam with 9 and 9.5 mm of PMMA thickness was not fully fragmented, rather its Bragg peak was very broad, allowing energy deposition that resulted in the largest number of induced SEUs per unit flux. Therefore, the beam still contained high-LET ions.

In addition, the SEU cross sections obtained with Kr ions and 31 mm PMMA thickness (for Cypress and Renesas memories) were more than one order of magnitude lower than those with 30.5 mm, consistent with the diode measurements and confirming that the Kr beam with 31 mm was fragmented. These results, from the diode and SRAM measurements, indicate that the SRIM energy and LET values are not accurate near the end of the ion range.

D. SEL cross sections

SEL measurements were performed during the spare time available after the SEU measurements. The SEL cross sections of the Samsung memory measured at HIMAC are reported in Fig. 8 in comparison with cross sections measured at HEARTS

from [11], and the corresponding numerical values are listed in Table III. The Xe SEL cross section is consistent with measurements from HEARTS, while those obtained with Kr ions show higher than expected sensitivity at lower LET, similar to the SEU cross sections.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

Tests on SRAMs performed at HIMAC with 178 MeV/n ^{132}Xe and 320 MeV/n ^{84}Kr ion beams allowed the measurement of SEU and SEL cross sections, as well as energy deposition events in a silicon diode, to improve understanding of the impact of high-energy heavy ions on electronic devices. The LET of the beam was varied by using PMMA degraders. The results were compared with those from other heavy ion facilities, highlighting the importance of facility inter-comparisons and the potential uncertainties in LET calculations for high-energy beams degraded by significant material thicknesses. In this regard, meaningful results were obtained with fragmented beams. Measurements with diodes and SRAMs indicate that SRIM energy and LET values are not accurate near the end of the ion range.

High-energy heavy ion beams have the significant advantage of allowing testing in air and without chip decapsulation. Although memories tested with the package, compared to delidded tests, typically showed SEU cross section differences within a factor of two, and in some cases, the differences reached several factors.

REFERENCES

- [1] R. García Alía *et al.*, “The HEARTS EU Project and Its Initial Results on Fragmented High-Energy Heavy-Ion Single-Event Effects Testing,” *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, vol. 72, no. 4, pp. 1040–1049, 2025.
- [2] S. Kodaira *et al.*, “Space radiation research with heavy ions at HIMAC,” *Life Sciences in Space Research*, vol. 43, pp. 4–12, 2024, life Sciences in Space Research Tenth Anniversary Special Issue. [Online]. Available: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S2214552424000798>
- [3] S. Yamada, “Commissioning and performance of the HIMAC medical accelerator,” in *Proceedings Particle Accelerator Conference*, vol. 1, 1995, pp. 9–13 vol.1.
- [4] T. Kanai *et al.*, “Cross-calibration of ionization chambers in proton and carbon beams,” *Physics in Medicine Biology*, vol. 49, no. 5, p. 771, feb 2004. [Online]. Available: <https://dx.doi.org/10.1088/0031-9155/49/5/008>
- [5] J. F. Ziegler *et al.*, “SRIM – The stopping and range of ions in matter (2010),” *Nuclear Instruments and Methods in Physics Research Section B: Beam Interactions with Materials and Atoms*, vol. 268, no. 11, pp. 1818 – 1823, 2010, 19th International Conference on Ion Beam Analysis. [Online]. Available: <http://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0168583X10001862>
- [6] N. Emriskova *et al.*, “Facility intercomparison towards reliable very-high-energy heavy ion dosimetry for space electronics testing at CERN,” *RADECS 2025*.
- [7] K. Bilko *et al.*, “Mixed-Field Radiation Monitoring and Beam Characterization Through Silicon Diode Detectors,” *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, vol. 71, no. 4, pp. 777–784, 2024.
- [8] K. Bilko *et al.*, “CHARM High-Energy Ions for Microelectronics Reliability Assurance (CHIMERA),” *IEEE Transactions on Nuclear Science*, vol. 71, no. 8, pp. 1549–1556, 2024.
- [9] W. E. Ricker, “The concept of confidence or fiducial limits applied to the poisson frequency distribution,” *Journal of the American Statistical Association*, vol. 32, no. 198, pp. 349–356, 1937. [Online]. Available: <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/abs/10.1080/01621459.1937.10502773>
- [10] A. Coronetti *et al.*, “SEU characterization of commercial and custom-designed SRAMs based on 90 nm technology and below,” in *2020 IEEE Radiation Effects Data Workshop (in conjunction with 2020 NSREC)*, 2020, pp. 1–8.

- [11] A. Coronetti *et al.*, “Results of Single Event Effect Testing at the New HEARTS@CERN High-Energy Heavy Ion Facility at CERN,” in *2024 IEEE Radiation Effects Data Workshop (REDW) (in conjunction with 2024 NSREC)*, 2024, pp. 1–9.
- [12] R. García Alía *et al.*, “Implications of Ion Fragmentation for High-Energy Heavy Ion Single Event Effects Testing,” *NSREC 2025*.

TABLE IV

ISSI 40 NM MEMORY - SEU CROSS SECTIONS MEASURED AT HIMAC WITH 178 MEV/N XE AND 320 MEV/N KR ION BEAMS, FOR DELIDDED AND PACKAGED MEMORIES. SEU: TOTAL BIT FLIPS (SBU + MBU); MBU: TOTAL BIT FLIPS FOR EVENTS WITH MULTIPLICITY ≥ 2

Ion	PMMA [mm]	LET SRIM [MeVcm ² /mg]	Delidded			$\sigma_{\text{delidded}}^{\text{SEU}}$ [cm ² /bit]	$\pm 2\sigma$ %	Packaged			$\sigma_{\text{packaged}}^{\text{SEU}}$ [cm ² /bit]	$\pm 2\sigma$ %
			SEU	SBU	MBU			SEU	SBU	MBU		
Xe	0	11.9	14221	10609	3612	$2.30 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	12138	12124	14	$1.96 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	5	16.2	14212	14196	16	$3.15 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	16408	16386	22	$3.64 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	7	22.7	14645	14621	24	$4.81 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	21340	17228	4112	$7.01 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	7.5	25.4	18505	18483	22	$5.16 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	22367	22323	44	$6.24 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	8	31.5	19731	19695	36	$5.76 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	34164	23547	10617	$9.98 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	10.5	frag ₃	3767	3767	0	$5.72 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	2922	2922	0	$4.44 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
Kr	0	3.6	14423	14397	26	$1.20 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	15124	15110	14	$1.26 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	20	5	26160	26144	16	$1.57 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	27327	27297	30	$1.64 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	25	6.14	13033	13021	12	$1.32 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	13598	13588	10	$1.37 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	28	7.65	35201	33798	1403	$2.44 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	40689	38478	2211	$2.66 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	30	9.9	39374	35239	4135	$4.11 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	43898	43746	152	$4.57 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	30.5	11.0	66867	63549	3318	$4.76 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	91492	90908	584	$6.47 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	31.5	frag ₅	8256	8252	4	$5.48 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10	10528	10522	6	$6.98 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10

TABLE V

CYPRESS 65 NM MEMORY - SEU CROSS SECTIONS MEASURED AT HIMAC WITH 178 MEV/N XE AND 320 MEV/N KR ION BEAMS, FOR DELIDDED AND PACKAGED MEMORIES. SEU: TOTAL BIT FLIPS (SBU + MBU); MBU: TOTAL BIT FLIPS FOR EVENTS WITH MULTIPLICITY ≥ 2

Ion	PMMA [mm]	LET SRIM [MeVcm ² /mg]	Delidded			$\sigma_{\text{delidded}}^{\text{SEU}}$ [cm ² /bit]	$\pm 2\sigma$ %	Packaged			$\sigma_{\text{packaged}}^{\text{SEU}}$ [cm ² /bit]	$\pm 2\sigma$ %
			SEU	SBU	MBU			SEU	SBU	MBU		
Xe	0	11.9	4649	1958	2691	$3.58 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	32930	12998	19932	$1.03 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10
	3.5	14.0	60235	23815	36420	$1.29 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10					
	4	14.6	180325	71712	108613	$2.06 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10					
	5	16.2	131487	52151	79336	$2.02 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10	86821	34453	52368	$1.19 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10
	7.5	25.4	155325	61156	94169	$3.58 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10	245840	92022	153818	$5.50 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10
	8	31.5	64481	25300	39181	$2.91 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10	308074	113616	194458	$6.89 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10
	8.5	47.4	14700	5773	8927	$1.84 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10					
	9	frag ₁	48402	19031	29371	$3.70 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10					
	9.5	frag ₂	68239	27326	40913	$6.71 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10					
	10.5	frag ₃	2268	854	1414	$5.34 \cdot 10^{-9}$	11	1699	686	1013	$3.23 \cdot 10^{-9}$	11
Kr	0	3.6	120404	48584	71820	$3.38 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	80481	32623	47858	$1.61 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	20	5.0	86239	34836	51403	$5.28 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	96328	39007	57321	$3.20 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	25	6.1						181606	73236	108370	$6.41 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10
	28	7.7						288314	116968	171346	$1.06 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10
	30	9.9	398373	150031	248342	$1.44 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10	325149	131608	193541	$1.64 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10
	30.5	11.0	422581	152291	270290	$2.96 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10	172822	68388	104434	$2.14 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10
	31	frag ₄						4800	2055	2745	$4.72 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10
	31.5	frag ₅	225928	91699	134229	$4.94 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10	25343	10472	14871	$7.03 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10
	32	frag ₆						4764	1964	2800	$4.98 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10

TABLE VI
 RENESAS 110 NM MEMORY - SEU CROSS SECTIONS MEASURED AT HIMAC WITH 178 MeV/N XE AND 320 MeV/N KR ION BEAMS, FOR DELIDDED
 AND PACKAGED MEMORIES. SEU: TOTAL BIT FLIPS (SBU + MBU); MBU: TOTAL BIT FLIPS FOR EVENTS WITH MULTIPLICITY ≥ 2

Ion	PMMA [mm]	LET SRIM [MeVcm ² /mg]	Delidded			$\sigma_{\text{delidded}}^{\text{SEU}}$ [cm ² /bit]	$\pm 2\sigma$ %	Packaged			$\sigma_{\text{packaged}}^{\text{SEU}}$ [cm ² /bit]	$\pm 2\sigma$ %
			SEU	SBU	MBU			SEU	SBU	MBU		
Xe	0	11.9	0	0	0	$<5.70 \cdot 10^{-12}$		0	0	0	$<2.31 \cdot 10^{-12}$	
	3.5	14.0	11	11	0	$4.73 \cdot 10^{-12}$	${}_{-51}^{+79}$					
	4	14.6	42	42	0	$9.59 \cdot 10^{-12}$	${}_{-28}^{+35}$					
	5	16.2	102	102	0	$3.14 \cdot 10^{-11}$	10	4	4	0	$1.09 \cdot 10^{-12}$	${}_{-75}^{+155}$
	7.5	25.4	981	977	4	$4.52 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10	499	483	16	$1.95 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10
	8	31.5	963	949	14	$8.68 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10	1204	1158	46	$5.38 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10
	8.5	47.4	568	550	18	$1.42 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10					
	9	frag ₁	1559	1449	110	$2.39 \cdot 10^{-9}$	10					
	9.5	frag ₂	5671	3998	1673	$1.12 \cdot 10^{-8}$	10					
	10.5	frag ₃	189	157	32	$8.89 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10	107	99	8	$4.07 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10
Kr	0	3.6						0	0	0	$<1.48 \cdot 10^{-13}$	
	20	5.0						0	0	0	$<2.46 \cdot 10^{-13}$	
	25	6.1						0	0	0	$<2.61 \cdot 10^{-13}$	
	28	7.7						26	26	0	$1.92 \cdot 10^{-12}$	${}_{-35}^{+46}$
	30	9.9						362	332	30	$3.65 \cdot 10^{-11}$	15
	30.5	11.0						1541	1505	36	$3.81 \cdot 10^{-10}$	11
	31	frag ₄						120	116	4	$2.36 \cdot 10^{-11}$	21
	31.5	frag ₅						219	205	14	$1.21 \cdot 10^{-11}$	17
	32	frag ₆						65	65	0	$1.36 \cdot 10^{-11}$	27
Kr	0	3.6						0	0	0	$<2.08 \cdot 10^{-13}$	
	20	5.0						0	0	0	$<4.53 \cdot 10^{-13}$	
	30	9.9						474	410	64	$3.43 \cdot 10^{-11}$	14
	30.5	11.0						4300	4172	128	$6.01 \cdot 10^{-10}$	10
	31.5	frag ₅						574	552	22	$2.51 \cdot 10^{-11}$	13